

MEDICAL SCIENCES

TREATMENT OF EROSIVE AND ULCERATIVE LESIONS OF THE ORAL MUCOSA THROUGH THE USE OF LOCAL ESITROPIC THERAPY

Zeynalova Zh.,

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant
Department of Therapeutic Dentistry*

Aliyev M.,

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine
Department of Therapeutic Dentistry Assistant*

Ashrafov D.

*Department of Orthopedic Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University,
Baku, Azerbaijan*

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Abstract

Today, about 70% of all violations of the integrity of the oral mucosa encountered in dental practice are necrotizing ulcerative gingivostomatitis [5–26]. Vincent's ulcerative-necrotizing gingivostomatitis is a terative-inflammatory process of the oral mucosa (OMP) of infectious etiology, occurring against the background of reduced reactivity of the body [2.4; 6, 10]. In the literature, this disease is described under different names: ulcerative gingivitis and stomatitis, ulcerative necrotic stomatitis, ulcerative membranous stomatitis, fuso-spirochetal stomatitis, Plaut-Vinsan stomatitis, ulcerosis, etc.

Keywords: *ulcerative-necrotizing gingivostomatitis, microbiological studies, species composition of microflora, associations of microorganisms.*

Ulcerative stomatitis - stomatitis ulcerosa was known in ancient times. According to descriptions, in 401 BC. e. As the army of the Greek commander Xenophon retreated from Asia, a disease spread - ulcers appeared in the soldiers' mouths, and their breath became foul. This disease was probably ulcerative stomatitis [8]. One of the oldest descriptions of this disease survives from the last decade of the 18th century. The French military doctor Degen describes the course and symptoms of this disease, which he observed during the Italian campaign of the French. Frunval in 1889 called this disease ulcerative stomatitis and gave its exact clinical description. German physician Plaut and French physician and bacteriologist Vincent in 1894 and 1895. independently found spindle-shaped bacilli and a spirochete in ulcers [8, 10]. During the two world wars, cases of ulcerative stomatitis were also often observed; the disease was called "trench disease" [9]. The cause of this disease, according to many authors, is the symbiosis of opportunistic microorganisms - spindle bacillus and Vincent's spirochete (*F. nucleatum* and *T. Vincentii*) [1.2.5]. These microorganisms are classified as opportunistic. Normally, they are present in significant quantities in the dentogingival sulcus, interdental spaces, periodontal pockets, carious cavities, root canals of teeth and tonsil crypts [9, 10, 11]. their number increases to such an extent that they become dominant compared to other microflora [7.12]. A sharp decrease in the body's resistance can occur against the background of hypothermia, stress, injury, surgical interventions, etc. - it cannot act as a reliable barrier to the introduction of infection, but a violation of its integrity, which always occurs in an unsanitized oral cavity due to the presence of local traumatic factors (sharp teeth,

dentures, poor hygiene). Therefore, ulcerative necrotizing stomatitis often develops in people with an unsanitized oral cavity and poor hygiene. many authors, there is a symbiosis of *F. nucleatum* and *T. Vincentii*. This opinion is based on the fact that in all cases with Vincent's ulcerative-necrotic gingivostomatitis, scrapings from the surface of the ulcers reveal spindle-like rods and spirochetes in huge quantities and sharply predominate over other. Fusobacteria and spirochaetes are anaerobes, located not only on the surface of the ulcer, in the deep areas of plaque, but also inside the tissues. It has been noted that it is spirochetes that penetrate most deeply into the living tissues surrounding the ulcer, located between the epithelial cells, which emphasizes their special importance in this stomatitis [6]

However, despite the constant presence of *F. nucleatum* and *T. Vincentii* in ulcerative necrotizing gingivostomatitis, the leading role of fusospiral symbiosis in the occurrence of this disease is not recognized by all scientists [6]. Despite the use of modern antibacterial drugs in local therapy of necrotic ulcers, their treatment remains one of the most important in dentistry. There has been a steady increase in the level of this disease, possibly due to insufficient study of its etiology [3]. Therefore, to select means of local etiotropic therapy for this disease, the purpose of this study was to study the species composition of the microflora of the oral mucosa in patients with necrotic ulcerative disease. gingi-vostomatitis. Materials and research methods Microbiological research was carried out in the laboratory of medical microbiology of the Institute of Epidemiology and Infectious Diseases named after L.V. To conduct the study, material was taken from 12 patients with necrotizing ulcerative gingivostomatitis. The material

for the study is the content of pathological lesions in patients with ulcerative necrotizing gingivostomatitis. Amies transport medium ("Transport medium w/Charcoal" (HIMEDIA, India) and transported to the laboratory. Primary inoculation of biological material for the isolation of anaerobic microorganisms was carried out on Wilkinson-Chaldgrin medium, 5% blood agar and thioglyone. Inoculation on solid nutrient media was carried out quantitative method of sector inoculation according to Gold. GENbox anaer (BioMerieux, France.) A plate with 5% blood agar was incubated under aerobic conditions at 37°C for 24 hours. After incubation, the growth of colonies in the plates was assessed. Colonization was determined for each individual bacterial species. Colony morphology, color, consistency, size, presence of hemolysis were studied, Gram stained. One, well isolated colony of each morphotype was selected and subcultured on Wilkinson-Chaldgreen medium under anaerobic conditions and on 5% blood agar under aerobic conditions. The microorganism was considered an anaerobic if there was growth under anaerobic conditions and no growth under aerobic conditions. Growth of microorganisms under anaerobic conditions was assessed after 48 hours of incubation. Colony morphology was studied, Gram stained, one well isolated colony of each morphotype was selected and subcultured on Wilkinson-Chaldgreen medium for anaerobic incubation and on blood agar for aerobic incubation. Microorganisms were considered anaerobic if there was growth under anaerobic conditions and no growth under aerobic conditions. Primary identification of anaerobic microorganisms was carried out using identification discs - An-ident Discs: erythromycin (60 µg), rifampicin (15 µg), colistin (10 µg) b penicillin (2 units), kanamycin (1000 µg), 0)("OXOID", Great Britain). For final identification, commercial test systems API 20 A (BioMerieux, France) were used.

When identifying the isolated microorganisms, the Bergi classification was followed. Results During microbiological studies, representatives of both resident (permanent) and transient (non-permanent, temporary) microflora were isolated and identified in all patients. A total of 110 strains were isolated, belonging to 21 types of microorganisms of various taxonomic groups. In all examined patients, microorganisms were isolated from different associations. Thus, in 24.3% of patients, the associations consisted of representatives of aerobic, anaerobic and fungal microflora, and in 75.7% - only of aerobic and anaerobic. On average, each surveyed association consisted of 7 to 9 types of microorganisms.

During the collection of material from patients with ulcerative necrotizing gingivostomatitis, representatives of resident microflora predominated, namely facultative anaerobic streptococci of the oral cavity (*S. salivarius*, *S. sanguis*, *S. mitis*, *S. mutans*), anaerobic cocci (*Peptococcus* spp.) and anaerobic streptococci

(*Peptostreptococcus* spp.), but a slightly lower percentage of their isolation has been recorded. , the growth rate of pathogenic staphylococcus *S. Aureus* is 41.7%. Representatives of the family Enterobacteriaceae were isolated in only 33.3%. It should be noted that the anaerobes *F. nucleatum* and *T. Vincentii*, the symbiosis of which is considered an etiological factor in the development of the ulcerative-necrotic process of the oral mucosa, were isolated in approximately one year. Thus, *F. nucleatum* was sown in 66.7% of cases, *T. Vincentii* – in 58.3%.

Conclusions New data have been obtained on the etiological factor in the development of erosive and ulcerative diseases of the oral mucosa of infectious etiology, belongs to the non-symbiosis of *F. nucleatum* and *T. vincentii*, but to an association of 7–9 microorganisms (aerobic, anaerobic and fungal microflora).

- microorganisms (aerobic, anaerobic and fungal microflora

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